

Exploring Factors Limiting Girls' Participation in Primary School Education: A Case of Sumbawanga District, Tanzania

Jabiri Bakari Mtulia ✉

Department of Education, Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University, Zanzibar, Tanzania

Abdallah Rajabu Mbega

Kanda Secondary School, Sumbawanga Municipal, Rukwa, Tanzania

Abstract

The study employed a mixed-methods research approach and specifically a cross-sectional survey design. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used in selecting 114 respondents and 10 public primary schools. The sample comprised head teachers, other teachers, school management committee (SMC) chairpersons, ward education co-ordinators (WEC), district education officer (DEO), faith-based organizations (FBOs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), parents, and pupils in school. Data were collected through questionnaires, interview schedules, documentary review and focus group discussions (FGDs). Qualitative data was subjected to thematic analysis to develop common themes, while quantitative data was analysed descriptively by using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The study established that the main factors that limited girls' full participation in schools were orphan hood due to loss of parents, poverty, school factors, domestic activities and parental preferences given to male children in education. Based on the results, the study suggests that the government should promptly remove these barriers by implementing comprehensive educational initiatives to address prejudices and promote girls' education.

Keywords: *Girls, Primary School Education.*

Suggested citation: Mtulia, J.B., & Mbega, A.R. (2024). Exploring Factors Limiting Girls' Participation in Primary School Education: A Case of Sumbawanga District, Tanzania. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(4), 99-114. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(4).09

Introduction

The problem of girls' limited participation in primary school education is a worldwide concern (Newmann, Wehlage, & Lamborn, 1992). The problem has affected all sectors in both developed and developing countries. Melville (2006) indicates that, in the US, the magnitude of the problem was grave before the 2000s. As a result, measures such as the use of "learning to finish campaign," and "Shelbyville's strategy," and a carrot-and-stick initiative, among others, were aimed at convincing pupils not to drop out of

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school. Furthermore, agreements with local employers as a measure also were reached so that pupils in school were strictly prohibited from seeking jobs until they had graduated. Bickel and Pagaiannis (1988) demonstrate that communities can influence dropout rates by providing employment opportunities during school.

The European Union (EU) also faced similar problems as 12.7 percent of enrolled girl students ended up being early school leavers (European Commission 2009). In Sub-Saharan Africa, girls have generally been denied their right to full participation in education (Iversen, 2012). Indeed, there is evidence that girls' rights to full participation to education have been violated. In countries such as Ethiopia, for example, particularly in the regional states of Amhara and Oromia, girls reaching maturity or puberty might be withdrawn from school (Molteno *et al.*, 2000). Also in Uganda, many girls fail to participate effectively in formal education while others dropout of primary school altogether due to poor sanitation facilities, especially when they start their menstruation periods (Uganda Government, 1992).

In the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), studies indicated that 46 percent of the girl students are victims of sexual harassment, abuse and violence from their teachers or other school personnel (UNICEF, 2004). According to the study by Iversen (2012) in Niger, 88 percent of participating teachers confirmed the existence of sexual acts between students and teachers at their school. Violence and the fear of violence in and around schools directly work against girls' enrolment, participation, completion and achievement.

In Tanzania, like in other developing countries in Sub-Sahara Africa, many of the girls do not have access to primary school education (Temba *et al.*, 2013). Holmes (2003) also found that overall girls attain less education and tend to drop out earlier than boys do. In response to this problem, various governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) have been taking measures to solve it since the country's independence from Britain in 1961. These measures include the Education Act of 1962 passed by the Tanganyika government to regulate the provision of education. This Act repealed and replaced the 1927 Education Ordinance and was intended to restructure the country's education system to ensure universal access to education for all children. Moreover, in 1967 the government introduced the philosophy of Education for Self-Reliance (ESR) to guide the planning and practice of education.

Furthermore, between 1967 and 1978, the government took several steps and enacted pertinent laws. Its measures included the introduction of Universal Primary Education (UPE) in 1974 to achieve full access to primary education for all school-age boys and girls (Ndaru, 1980). In 1995, Tanzania formulated its Education and Training Policy (ETP), which also re-emphasised UPE. Salient features of the ETP include the decentralisation of the management and administration of primary education to local government and communities, compulsory enrolment of all school-age children and full attendance (MoEC, 1995).

Moreover, there was a push towards the expansion of schools and increasing of enrolment rates. School fees were abolished and government made concerted efforts to provide instructional materials to schools. Its key interventionist programmes include the Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP) of 2002/06 and 2007/11, for phase I and II, respectively. Furthermore, Tanzania has been implementing various international and domestic instruments, such as the Beijing platform for action of 1995. It had earlier taken part in the international conference convened in 1990 in Jomtien, Thailand which launched the education for all (EFA)

global movement to ensure that all children were provided with basic education by 2000 (UNESCO, 2011). Similarly, it took part in the world education forum that ran from 26 to 28 April 2000 in Dakar, Senegal, which set the goal of achieving achievement of Education for All by 2015 and also pushed for the achievement of universal primary education by 2015 (Aderinoye, 2000).

Despite all these national and international governmental and non-governmental measures, the problem of lack of universal full participation for girls in primary schools has persisted. Particularly in Rukwa region where by 193 female pupils and 145 girls students of secondary schools drop out from school with different factors (National Bureau of Statistics, 2013). In connection to that, Sumbawanga district where the study conducted 239 registered female pupils are absent from school with different reasons such as truancy, early pregnant, domestic chores and other factors like those who feel shy to repeat standard four after failure of national examination (Mutasingwa, 2014). It appears that the existing measures have failed to tackle the underlying causes behind the problem of limited participation of girls in primary schools. This study investigated this area. Additionally, there is a need to examine the manner and extent of planning on matters affecting their academic well-being. It is on these grounds that this study was conducted to examine the strategies used to address the factors that preventing the full participation of girls in Tanzania's primary schools using Sumbawanga district as a case study.

Objective of the Study

Specifically, the study aimed to investigate the underlying factors contributing to limited girls' participation in primary school education.

Research Methods

Location of the Study

The study was conducted in Sumbawanga District in Rukwa Region of Tanzania. The selection of this study area (Sumbawanga District) was influenced primarily by one major reason: it represents rural areas where girls are denied their right to education. This area was thus vital [because of its trends for girl pupil dropout from school and/or irregular attendance] for studying and examining the underlying factors for purposes of finding solutions to the problem.

Research Approach

This study used a mixed-methods research approach that combined the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data during the process of data collection. Johnson *et al* (2007) define a "mixed methods research" as the type of research in which a researcher or team of researchers combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches. Qualitative research approach helped the researcher to get in-depth, contextualised, and natural insights of qualitative data concerning the views and perceptions of participants on constraints limiting the full participation of girls in primary school through interviews and focus group discussions. The choice of the quantitative approach, on the other hand was based on the fact that, using closed-ended questions allowed the researcher to gather broad and quantifiable data on the factors limiting the girls' full participation in primary school.

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey specifically cross-sectional survey, study design. The study employed the cross-section survey because of its capacity to collect information from a sample that has been drawn from a pre-determined population at a single point in time, hence saving time. Requisite data were obtained from different locations from a sample of 114 respondents using different categories of people (Head teachers, teachers, Ward education co-ordinators, parents, pupils, chairpersons of school management committee, the District Education Officer and representatives from non-governmental organisations and Faith based organizations) during a small interval of time in 2015. Cohen *et al.* (2000) argue that a descriptive survey is useful because it gathers data in a short time and, hence, is economical and efficient. In addition, it generates descriptive and explanatory information.

Target Population

The targeted population from this study comprised of pupils, parents/guardians, teachers and heads of school, the Ward Education co-ordinators, chairperson from the school management committee and a representative from Non-governmental organisations, Faith-based organisations and the District education officer.

Sampling Strategies

The researcher employed simple random sampling as a one of the four types of probability sampling technique and purposive sampling as one of non-probability sampling. Simple random sampling is a probability sampling technique whereby all members in the population have an equal chance of being selected to form a sample (Adam *et al.*, 2008). This method was used to select the sample of schools and girl pupils from the sampling frame. On the other hand, purposive sampling used to select pupils, and teachers, heads of school, who deal with day-to-day affairs of the pupils and District Education Officer responsible for primary education. Also researcher used purposive sampling method to select chairperson of the school management committee and representatives from NGOs and FBOs.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

A Sample size refers to the number of items to be selected from the universe to constitute a sample (Kothari, 1990). Sampling technique involves a process of selecting a sub-section of a population that represents the entire population for purposes of obtaining information on the phenomenon of interest

Sample of the Study and Sample Size

The study involved the sample of 103 public primary schools in Sumbawanga District. Out of these schools the researcher drew a sample size of ten (10) public primary schools, an equivalent of to 10 percent of the total. The study also involved a sample size of one hundred and fourteen (114) respondents, that were included one (1) head teacher from each sampled public primary schools, hence a total of ten (10) head teachers; five (5) ward education co-ordinators, made up of three males and two females; two (2) representatives from non-governmental organisations and another two (2) from faith-based organization; two (2) chairpersons of the school management committee drawn from the ten (10) selected primary schools, two (2) parents (1 male and 1 female) of pupils attending the ten (10) selected primary schools. In addition, the study involved three (3) selected teachers from each sampled public primary school, a total of thirty (30) teacher respondents. The study also involved one (1) District Education Officer (DEO) for primary education. Furthermore, from each of

the ten schools six (6) pupils were selected, hence a total of sixty (60) pupils who took part in this study. Determination of sample size depends on the research design. For the purpose of this study, a sample size determination formula for infinite populations (unknown) was applied to get a sample size of one hundred and fourteen (114) respondents.

The following sample size formula for an infinite population was used to arrive at a representative number of respondents (Godden, 2004):

$$SS = \frac{Z^2 \times (P) \times (1-P)}{C^2}$$

Where:

SS= Sample Size for an infinite population (more than 50,000);

Z = Z-value (e.g., 1.96 for a 95 percent confidence level);

P = Proportion of population picking a choice, expressed as decimal; and

C = Confidence interval, expressed as decimal (e.g., .04 = +/- 4 percentage points)

Example.

From this study, Population proportion= 99024,

Assumed percentage of population picking a choice to be 95 percent

Confidence interval (margin of error) 4% = 0.04

Z-value = 1.96.

Now,

$$SS = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.95 \times (1-0.95)}{(0.04)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.95 \times 0.005}{0.0016} = \frac{0.182476}{0.0016}$$

Sample size is 114.0475 = 114.

Generally, the selection of the respondents in this study was based on the nature of study, time availability and type of sampling procedures so as to get accurate information and data.

Materials and Methods

In this study, the researcher employed a structured questionnaire, focus group discussion and in-depth interview schedule to collect primary data. Secondary data was collected through documentary review.

Structured Questionnaire Survey

The researcher used a structured questionnaire to collect data from the projected thirty (30) respondents that is three (3) teachers from each school. All the questions were closed ended and administered by the researcher. The structured questionnaire was used to collect data on the number of girl pupils who dropped out of school, the

attendance girl pupils to establish whether it improved after the introduction school strategies and the extent to which some factors, contributed to the problem of limited girl's participation. Three teachers were selected from each school and were given a questionnaire to fill in their appropriate responses.

Focus Group Discussion

Focus group discussion (FGD) is a way of collecting qualitative data. It promotes interaction among participants that stimulates them to state feelings, perception and beliefs that they would otherwise not express if they are interviewed individually (Denscombe, 1998). In this study, the researcher used a simple random technique to select about ten (10) primary schools from which sixty (60) female pupils in standard VI and VII classes were selected to take part in the FGDs.

In-depth Interviews

An interview guide was used to collect related information from primary schools' District Education Officer, Ward Education Co-ordinators and head teachers in the sampled primary schools, parents, representatives from social organisation and chair-person of the school management committee. The interviews centered on the factors that limit girls' full participation in primary education, the effectiveness of the strategies employed by the government in education and the extent to which the school employed measures to reduce the problem as well as the contribution of social organisation in solving the problem.

Documentary Review

This method was used to collect secondary data. In this study, the researcher reviewed various public records, as documents including inspectorate reports, attendance registers, cumulative register files, pupils' discipline files, staff meeting files, lesson plans, school committee files, files for rules and regulations introduced by the government and the school strategic plan. These documents were reviewed to identify the absenteeism rate among female pupils, dropout cases, disciplinary problems that affect the girl-children's participation in school activities, teacher's recommendation on pupils' attendance rate and school inspection recommendation on primary school girls' participation enhancement strategies. Moreover, the researcher used public records, as documents are stable and, therefore, can be reviewed repeatedly to provide the same information. Documentary analysis review was used to supplement information from the questionnaire survey and interviews.

Data Analysis Plan

The data obtained from the field, were analysed in accordance with the methods employed to collect the data. In this study, for consistency purposes, all filled out questionnaires were rechecked for completeness. Manual data cleaning was conducted to check for accuracy and completeness of the questionnaires. The quantitative data were descriptively analysed with the help of using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The outputs were then presented in tables of frequencies and percentages, pie-charts and bar-charts. On the other hand, data collected from interviews and FGDs, were analysed qualitatively and subjected to content analysis. Relevant information was extracted, following the Miles and Huberman (1994) model of qualitative data analysis. Content analysis involved reading through the transcribed texts of each in-depth interview and identifying responses relevant to the study's main questions. Finally, a combination of graphical, tabular and narrative presentation was used to present both quantitative and qualitative data.

Validation of Instruments

To ensure validity and reliability researchers employed triangulation whereby interviews, documentary review, questionnaires and focus group discussions are employed as a multiple data collection instruments. Thus, the use of different instruments enabled the researcher to avoid biasness, enhance confidence in the field during data collection and analysis. Furthermore, before field research a pilot study was conducted at two schools, which were not included in the study sample, where two heads of school, eight pupils, that is four pupils from each school provided 4 students and 6 teachers three each school and one parent took part. The researcher tested the instruments and find out that, some questions in questionnaire and interview guides do not well understood. Therefore, researcher modified them accordingly to reduce ambiguity.

Ethical Considerations

The study observed all ethical rules and followed procedures to enhance human rights of all participants. The researcher adhered to all protocols including the procedures required for the one to conduct research. On the other hand, before inviting respondents to take part in the study, the researcher informed the participants about the research topic, its significance, purpose, objectives and the meaning of the study to give them freedom of expression during data collection. In addition, the respondents were assured of their personal protection and that, they had authority to refuse or accept to participate in the study. To observe confidentiality during data processing, the researcher ensured that, data obtained was used for academic purposes only and the respondent were not identified in any way with the information they had provided.

Results, Discussion and Findings

Knowledge on Girls' Education Participation

The study sought to indicate whether the respondents were knowledgeable enough about the meaning of girls' full participation in primary education. The responses from 54 respondents made up of 10 heads of school, 5 education co-ordinators and 30 teachers, as well as representatives from NGOs, FBOs and CBOs and parents, are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Respondent's Awareness of the meaning of pupils' Full Participation in Education (N=30)

Source: Field Data (2015)

As the figure illustrates, of all the 30 teachers who filled out the questionnaire 50 percent agreed that pupils' full participation involves classroom attendance, performing and undertaking extra-curricular activities as well as completing primary school education. 30 percent of the teachers did not agree with the statement while the remaining 20 percent were not sure. The findings mean that some of the respondents were not aware of the meaning of full participation in education. This might be due to their level of education or their limited work experience. Therefore, a lot has to be done to raise awareness of the respondents on the meaning of full participation in education. On other hand the District Education Officer seemed to agree with this need for raising the awareness when he said,

....Some teachers are not familiar with what exactly it means by full participation of pupils in education. They think if a student attends a classroom session, that is enough but a teacher should know that full participation is beyond mere classroom attendance... (Interview, District Education Officer).

In other words, some teachers were not aware of what constitutes full pupils' participation in education. Basically, education is not only about attending classes but also about performance and undertaking extra-curricular activities as well as completing the primary school education cycle. For girls, full participation would mean that they were enjoying all factors as mentioned above, plus "emancipation" from traditional factors such as initiation rites, domestic chores, early marriage and taking care of younger siblings. Also it includes improvement of accessibility, enrolment and an increase in awareness of their surrounding environment. The implication of these study findings is that, in cases many teachers were became teachers by default and not because they were dedicated to the profession so as to get to grips with all the rudiments of the profession. As a result, they did not even review what is required in their profession. Therefore, the government should revisit the existing curricular, motivate the teachers by paying them teaching allowance and other emoluments in addition to careful recruitment of qualified and dedicated teachers able to provide competence-based education. This finding is in consonant with findings by Mosha (2004) who established that there was a need to develop teachers' professional development programmes in form of in-service training or continuing education programmes. After all, well-qualified teachers are factors in improving the quality of education.

Furthermore, another interviewee, who was also a chairperson of school management committee, in the same vein said:

The majority of the parents also do not understand what exactly it means by full participation for pupils in education. They think that if a pupil wears a uniform and goes to school, that is enough, but as a parent/guardian, full participation goes beyond that. (Interview, Chairperson of School C).

The implication is that, parents/guardians did not understand clearly what full participation of pupils in education entails. Thus, they decide to take their children out of school for some time during school hours and let them stay home to take care of their younger brothers and other siblings when their parents go to the farm. Therefore, this becomes a factors limited participation of girls in primary school. This finding is in line with Velkoff (1998) who observed that 45 percent of girls enrolled in primary school drop out to help with family responsibilities such as caring for younger siblings and/or are taken out of school when they reach puberty as a way of protecting their honour. The study findings imply that, the government and key education stakeholders

have to work to do to educate parents/guardians on the importance of education for their children, particularly girls. The existing measures should also enforce parents, teachers and students to reduce the girls' limited participation problem.

Barriers to Girls, Full Participation in Primary School Education

The study aimed to explore the respondents' views on factors contributing to limited participation of girls in primary school education. To obtain relevant information in-depth interviews, questionnaires and documentary review were conducted. The findings are as presented under following sub-headings:

Socio-cultural Factors

Under this sub-section the study explored the influence of socio-cultural factors on girls' full participation in primary education. Questionnaires were administered with teachers in primary schools under the study. The respondents were asked to agree or disagree with the given statements. The findings are presented in Table 1:

Table 1. Socio-Cultural Factors

Statement Associated with Traditional Beliefs	Teachers (N=30)	
	F	%
Gender stereotyping	24	80.0
Preferences for sons	26	86.6
Domestics activities	30	100.0
Taking care of young siblings	26	86.6
Early marriage	13	43.3
Early pregnancy	27	90.0

Source: Field Data (2015).

The table shows that most of the teachers mentioned domestic activities, early pregnancy and early marriage as socio-cultural practice factors inhibiting the full participation of girls in primary school education. They said that some of the parents discouraged females from continuing with primary school education and forced them to get married instead because they were afraid they could get early pregnancy. On the other hand, teachers observed that girls sometimes began working at an earlier age than boys and girls also tended to do more household chores than boys. They also said that some girls tend to drop out of school to take care of their younger siblings. It was also established that if mothers worked outside the home, girls shouldered some responsibilities of the household which made them drop out. During focus group discussion (FGD) with female pupils from selected primary schools, the researcher identified an array of socio-cultural practices that hindered females from fully participating in primary school education. Most of the girls said, some of the girls in their area got married early, some as young as 12. Most of the female pupils also confirmed that girls were assigned more responsibilities than boys, especially domestic responsibilities such as cooking and fetching water for the family. One girl said:

....when we arrive at home from school with my elder brothers, I am the one who does all the home activities such as cooking food, fetching water, collecting firewood and looking after our younger brothers and sisters (FGD, girl-pupil of school A).

Another girl said:

After we wake up in the morning, I am the one who cleans the house, sets the fire, prepares tea, and fetches water if the water I fetched the previous day is not enough for the whole day, despite having three brothers. This makes me feel very tired and several times I go to school very late causing me to doze off in the classroom (FGD, girl-pupils of school D).

It is apparent that in such homes, girls are overwhelmed by domestic responsibilities. Home responsibilities make girls either miss school or go to school late or feel too tired to remain awake in the classroom. These findings were supported by findings from interviews held with parents. All the parents interviewed admitted that they assigned more responsibilities, especially home activities, to girls than to boys. In other words, many parents still uphold traditional beliefs that all domestic chores are for girls and women. One female parent remarked:

A female child is a mother-to-be so she should do all mothers' activities such as cooking food or fetching water as early as possible... It is hard for a boy child to do such activities... a girl-child has more to do at home than a boy-child and this is our tradition and there is nothing else we can do about it (Interview, female parent).

Parents also declared that they were also ready to marry off their daughters, out of fear of their becoming pregnant before marriage, something that was a shame to the parents. In support of this argument, one old male parent said:

If a suitor shows up to marry my daughter, who is schooling I will accept him because if I refuse my child might become pregnant, making us miss the bride-wealth and having the daughter kicked out of studies (Interview, male old parent).

In most of the African traditional societies marriage among daughter is considered as a source of income. This argument concurs with a study by Odaga and Heneveld (1995) who found that parents worry about wasting money on the education of girls because of fear that girls can be impregnated or get married before completing their schooling. Once girls get married, they become part of another family. In other words the parental investment in forms of money, energy and other resources is lost.

The District Education Officers revealed that gender stereotyping was a traditional belief that adversely affected girls' participation in primary school education. In this regard, the Education officer noted:

In this area, community members still do not value education of a girl-child as they do for the boy-child. Most of the parents are ready to invest much in education for their sons and not for their daughters and hence are willing to ask a girl-child to remain at home to perform roles of mothers while sending the boy-child to school (Interview, Ward Education Officer).

In this regard, the parents in the communities visited were willing to let the female children remain at home and perform domestic roles as their male children attended schools, hence sacrificing their education prospects in the process. When heads of school were asked the same question on the traditional beliefs that hindered the female children's full participation in primary school education, two heads mentioned domestic chores, early pregnancies and traditional dances. Two other heads of school indicated the girls playing double roles of shouldering (i) family roles and obligations, and (ii) academic obligations at the same time. Given their tender age, these girls were forced to become adults at the time when they were supposed to be thinking only about school. Ultimately, such heavy responsibilities placed on their tender shoulders took their toll and more often than not, let their education suffer. This finding is in line with the findings by Baki (2004) who reported that in the Middle East and North

Africa, socio-cultural traditions such as early marriage, child bearing and unwillingness to allow girls to travel over long distances have contributed to low participation of women in education in those regions. This pattern of educational provision and attendance is echoed in other regions of the developing world. In Nepal, for example, early marriage and motherhood account for 40 percent of the girls who got married before the age of 15 (UNESCO, 2003). Similarly, Uganda Participatory Poverty Assessment (UPPAP, 2000) indicates that marrying off a girl would benefit her family in terms of attaining the bride price. Concurrently, it was established that early marriages were still being practiced in Tanzania despite the existing laws, which make it an offence for any person to marry a school-girl (United Republic of Tanzania, 1978).

School-based Factors Inhibiting Girls' Full Participation

Under this sub-section, the study sought to explore school-based factors contributing to the limited participation of female pupils in primary school education in Sumbawanga District. Table 2 summarises the findings from a questionnaire administered with teachers.

Table 2. Teachers' Views on School-based Factors Affecting Girls' Participation in Primary Education

Factors	Teachers (n=30)	
	F	%
School contributions	26	86.6
Distance to school	25	83.3
Gender based violence	28	93.3
Lack of toilets	30	100.0
Fetching water and firewood for teachers	22	73.3
Cooking for teachers	26	86.6
Extra-curricular activities	19	63.3
Inadequate classrooms	11	36.6
Inadequate teachers in number	09	30.0

Source: Field Data (2015).

The table indicates that lack of enough toilet pits, gender-based violence, school contributions, cooking for teachers and long distance to school were the main school-related factors that curtailed the girls' full school participation in primary school education. This finding is also supported by finding from the FGDs with female pupils. Most of girls complained about lack of sanitary facilities and toilet pits during the FGDs. One girl noted:

In this school, we don't have enough toilet pits for pupils....what we have is just only one toilet separated with iron sheet...this situation is more compounded by lack of sanitary facilities, it is very difficult for me to come to school when not in a good condition [menstruation period].What I do is just to stay at home until I am fine again....this can take even three to five days (FGDs Girl Pupil of School E).

Likewise, interviews with head teachers said that the poor physical layout of the school, lack of water and poor sanitation contributed to low completion rate of basic education by girls. During an interview, one head of school said:

In this school we don't have enough toilet pits for all the pupil....the school ratio is almost 1:60 pupils. This situation affects female pupils' more than male pupils hence some of the female

pupils decide not to come to school when they are not in a good condition. We also lack other sanitary facilities, especially for girls (Interview, Head of School F).

In other words inadequate toilet pits, coupled with lack of sanitary facilities, affected the participation of girls in primary school education. This finding is in line with a study carried out by Molteno *et al.* (2000) who contends that in Uganda, many girls failed to participate effectively in formal education whereas others dropout of primary school altogether due to poor sanitation facilities, especially when they start their menstruation periods. In addition, Lizettee (2000) observes that lack of facilities and poor hygiene affect both girls and boys, with sanitation in schools having a strong negative impact on girls. Similarly, UNICEF (2006) reveals that in Africa, lack of basic sanitation is the cause of decreasing enrolment of girls in secondary schools as girls spend more time in schools with adequate sanitation facilities.

During interviews with the District Education Officer for primary schools and chairperson of school management committee it emerged that walking over long distances to and from school was also one of challenges to girls' participation in education. They said that some of the school girls lived some 8 or 9 kilometres away from schools, hence reached school too tired to pay much attention in class. This made them perform poorly in class, and the poor grades discouraged them so much that they opted out of school. Similar finding were reported by Omari (1995) who observed that the longer the distance from home to school the more the children were unwilling to walk over those long distances, especially during the long rains or scorching summer sun and cold season especially in the morning.

Household Source of Income

Household income refers to a measure of the combined incomes of all people sharing a particular household or place of residence. It is often used as an economic indicator of the socio-economic status of homes or households in a place of residence. In the case of this study, household sources of income help to indicate the economic status of the residents of the area of study, in this case of Rukwa region, as presented in Table 1.3 below.

Table 3. Rukwa Regional Share Contribution to the Gross Domestic Product and Per Capita Income, 1999 to 2010

YEAR	GDPIN '000,000 TZS		PER CAPITA INCOME	
	Tanzania Main land	Rukwa Region	Tanzania Main land	Rukwa Region
1999	7,222,560	269,877	233,397	255,080
2000	8,152,790	295,030	255,575	270,511
2001	9,100,274	297,632	276,741	264,731
2002	10,444,507	337,155	310,991	295,299
2003	12,107,062	429,981	353,496	367,565
2004	13,971,592	483,245	396,154	398,486
2005	15,965,294	547,334	441,063	437,274
2006	17,941,268	611,089	478,100	469,246
2007	20,948,403	724,781	547,081	537,042
2008	24,781,679	871,896	627,787	623,288
2009	28,212,646	974,823	693,470	672,237
2010	32,293,479	1,095,346	770,464	728,684
2011	37,532,962	1,293,386	869,436	830,052

Source: Rukwa regional office (2013). Rukwa investment profile

As it appears from the table above, in 2002 the regional gross domestic product (GDP) was 337,155 Mil TZS and per capita income of 295,299 TZS. In 2010 the GDP rose to 1,095,346 Mil TZS and the per capita income to TZS 728,684 which indicated Regional growth in Gross Domestic Product of 3.39%. This means that, the majority of peoples' income was below the line of extreme poverty of one dollar per day, taking into account that an average household size is 5.1.

Age dependency ratio is defined as the ratio of the youths younger than 15 years of age, plus persons aged 65 years and above (dependants) to adults aged between 15 and 64 years (workforce). According to the population and housing census (2002) in Rukwa region, the overall dependency ratio was 1:1. This means that there were 100 people in the 15-64 year group supporting 105 people in age group 0-14 and 65 and above. The age dependency ratio was higher in rural areas than in urban areas. The above finding as extracted from the population and the housing census of 2002 is further confirmed by focus group discussions (FGDs). For example, in the discussion it was revealed that poverty of households was a leading factor that limited the full participation of girls in primary school education in Sumbawanga District. It was established that most of the parents were too poor to cope with both the direct and hidden costs of girls' participation in schooling. In consequence, there were low levels of involvement and high levels of wastage. One girl noted:

My parents engage only in subsistence farming and sometimes in cattle rearing, hence they don't have much income to cover all school contributions.... In this school we are told to pay 5,000/= every month for food....and we pay 10,000/= for examination... All parents are also required to pay 10,000/= every year for school maintenance... This is very difficult because I also have my two sisters and two younger brothers in this school... (FGD, girl pupil of School C).

The study finding also shows that sometimes female students went to school without learning materials such as exercise-books and pens. As a result they failed to do exercises or homework provided by the teachers. They were punished by teachers the following day for failing to do assigned exercises. To avoid such punishment, many decided not to go to school. Similar findings were noted in an FGD with six girl pupils. One of them said:

It is only a miracle that I am here [at the school]. My parents are very poor; they only depend on subsistence farming. When I was enrolled at this school, I was so happy, but this education cost is too much for my parents....they don't have money to cover all I need for my education....I only come to school because my uncle is the chairman of this village....at least he supports me with some school contributions and he also buys me school uniforms and shoes. (FGD, girl pupils of school J).

In other words, the direct school cost for buying such items as exercise books, paper, writing materials, and textbooks and, sometimes, uniforms were prohibitive when it came to full participation of female pupils in primary school education. Interview with heads of school also revealed that many of the families of the school community were poor, making most of the pupils arrive at school without taking anything for breakfast. Such pupils looked weak and lacked classroom concentration. Inevitably, many of such schoolchildren had poor performance, irregular attendance and, ultimately, dropped out of school.

Through questionnaires, teachers said that Sumbawanga community members were generally poor, something which affected girls' education. About 25 (83.3%) said that most of parents' earnings from peasant farming were reduced by poor weather

conditions such as unreliable rainfall, hence forcing them to lose harvests. Eighteen others (60%) said parents/guardians refused to support the school feeding programme because of a dire, maiming poverty. As a result, schools failed to offer meals. These results correlate with what was established in a study by Gabagambi (2008) which indicates that the majority of Tanzanians depend on agriculture but earn generally so little that they are subjected to abject poverty. They failed to support their families economically, causing some of their children to drop out of school, as compared to the few pupils whose parents are economically better off and are of good standing.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study reveals that socio-cultural barriers, such as early pregnancy, early marriage, and domestic obligations, significantly hinder girls' participation in elementary school. Parents' reluctance to fund their daughters' education due to cultural norms and pregnancy concerns exacerbates this issue. Similarly, gender differences in domestic affairs further disadvantage females, leading to dropout rates. In addition, inadequate facilities, gender-based violence, and financial strains also make it difficult for girls to fully participate in primary education. On the other hand, poverty found to be the primary cause of these issues, contributing to high dropout rates and low participation rates among girls. A comprehensive method that addresses both socio-cultural norms and systemic impediments within educational institutions are necessary to achieve equitable access and retention. The government should swiftly eliminate these obstacles, providing comprehensive educational programs to combat stereotypes and support girls' education.

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